

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The influence of transformational leadership style on the implementation of patient safety in hospitals: Literature review

Badriyah Putri Jannah *

Department of Health Policy and Administration, Faculty of Public Health, Airlangga University, Surabaya, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 22(02), 1999–2004

Publication history: Received on 14 April 2024 revised on 26 May 2024; accepted on 29 May 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.22.2.1655>

Abstract

Hospitals, as health service facilities, have a top priority in pursuing patient safety as an organizational outcome. In this case, leaders have a proactive role in implementing patient safety as a means of preventing incidents related to hospital patient safety. A leader's leadership style needs to be adapted to the needs of the organization, one of which is the transformational leadership style. With the characteristics of hospitals as complex healthcare facilities, this leadership style is considered the most appropriate to apply. Objective: The aim of writing the article is to determine the influence of transformational leadership styles on efforts to implement patient safety in hospitals. Methodology: This paper uses a literature study method with secondary data in the form of journals and published articles sourced from online databases and adjusted to the specified inclusion and exclusion criteria. Results: Transformational leadership applied in hospitals is a very significant and positive strategy for patient safety efforts. Leaders with a transformational leadership style will focus on effective integration processes so they can provide high-quality patient care. Transformational leadership plays a role in improving working conditions and atmosphere. This will affect the quality of service and care provided by hospital staff to patients. The implementation of quality services has an impact on preventing and handling patient safety incidents. Conclusion: A significant influence on the leadership style exercised by a hospital leader positively impacts patient safety efforts.

Keywords: Transformational leadership; Patient safety; Leaders; Health Service; Hospitals.

1. Introduction

Hospitals, as health service facilities, have a top priority in pursuing patient safety as an organisational outcome. Patient safety is a top priority in health and nursing services, as well as being the most important aspect of quality management [1]. The health services that patients receive in hospitals are very complex and involve various scientific disciplines, tests, and treatment procedures, so this condition can cause unexpected events (KTD) [2]. Patient safety incidents will have negative impacts and losses for various parties, including hospitals and patients as customers. The impacts in question include death, impaired bodily function or disability, financial losses, and reduced public confidence in hospital services [3].

The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that the percentage of adverse events in hospitalized patients in various countries varies, namely from 3% to 16%. The percentage of KTD in New Zealand is around 12.9%; in England, it is around 10.8%; and in Canada, it is 7.5%. Meanwhile, the percentage of adverse events reported by the Joint Commission International (JCI) is around 10% in the United Kingdom and 16.6% in Australia [4]. Studies related to patient safety issues in Indonesia were first reviewed in 2000. The research in this study came from 4,500 medical records in 15 hospitals. The research results show that there are variations in the factors that cause KTD, namely diagnosis errors ranging between 8.0% and 98.2% and treatment errors with a percentage of 4.1%-91.6% [5]. In the following year, the

* Corresponding author: Badriyah Putri Jannah

number of patient safety incidents continued to increase. In 2019, there were 7,465 cases of patient safety incidents in Indonesia, including 171 deaths, 80 serious injuries, 372 moderate injuries, 1183 minor injuries, and 5659 no injuries [6].

Based on patient safety incident reporting data, which increases from year to year, patient safety climate is one of the important hospital visions and must always be improved. Hospital leaders need to improve the patient safety climate as a shared vision [7]. Patient safety is the main indicator for hospitals to provide the best health services, in realizing patient satisfaction as the organization's main goal. In this case, leaders have a proactive role in implementing patient safety as a means of preventing incidents related to hospital patient safety.

Every leader in an organization has a leadership style that is different from one another. The leadership style applied needs to be adapted to the needs of the organization. This is needed by every leader to realize the organizational goals that have been set. Leadership plays an important role in enabling teams to work effectively by communicating with each other. Great leaders can adapt and change their leadership style to ensure positive outcomes for staff and key stakeholders on the team [8]. One leadership style that is often applied in the hospital industry is transformational leadership.

Transformational leadership is defined as a theory of leadership where the leader creates an environment that is suitable for working and will increase the output of committed group members [9]. With the characteristics of hospitals as complex healthcare facilities consisting of a large number of various resources, this leadership style is considered the most appropriate to apply. Several literature reviews will be analyzed to determine the influence of transformational leadership styles on the implementation of patient safety in hospitals. It is hoped that the influence analysis through this study can become a reference source in determining the appropriate type or leadership style to be applied in the hospital work environment.

2. Material and methods

The descriptive literature review method with secondary data collection was used in writing this article. The literature review was carried out by collecting several journals and articles sourced from online databases, namely ScienceDirect and Google Scholar. Journals and articles use Indonesian and English. The author looks for references by entering keywords, namely "Transformational Leadership" "Patient Safety" AND "Hospital". To meet the inclusion criteria, article collection focused on original research articles published from 2019 to 2023; there were no country restrictions as research subjects and relevant studies regarding the influence of transformational leadership styles on patient safety efforts in hospitals. The exclusion criteria for articles are articles other than Indonesian and English, as well as articles with research data that do not match the topic of discussion. Based on the literature findings, the author used 5 (five) research articles, which will then be reviewed and concluded because they are considered relevant to the topic of discussion.

3. Results and discussion

Based on the results of article searches via online databases, 5 (five) articles meet the specified inclusion and exclusion criteria. The studies in the findings article were conducted in hospitals located in Indonesia ($n = 3$), Uzbekistan ($n > 1$), and Finland ($n = 3$). There is one article published in 2023, one article published in 2022, one article published in 2021, one article published in 2020, and one article published in 2019. The articles regarding transformational leadership and patient safety were then reviewed systematically. The results of the study are presented in the form of a summary table, as follows:

Table 1 List of articles

No.	Author	Research Title	Method	Result
1.	Syabanasyah <i>et al</i> [10]	The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Patient Safety Efforts	Cross sectional quantitative approach with 100 medical officers, nurses, and medical support	Transformational leadership influences patient safety culture with a t-statistical test of 2.80 and also influences patient safety efforts with a t-test of 2.26.

2.	Rizkia <i>et al</i> [11]	The Effect of Interprofessional Collaboration and Transformational Leadership on Patient Safety with Work Motivation as Intervening Variables	Cross sectional with 250 nurses participating in this research	Interprofessional collaboration and transformational leadership have a positive and significant effect on work motivation and patient safety.
3.	Gao & Tangatarova [12]	Transformational Leadership and Patient Safety In Hospitals: The Roles of Safety Culture, Decision-Making Capacity, and Locus of Control	Cross sectional with 240 nurses participating in this research	There is a significant role of transformational leadership in improving working conditions and the environment in terms of creating positive patient relationships and improving patient safety
4.	Azuma <i>et al</i> [13]	The Influence of Transformational Leadership and Motivation on the Implementation of Patient Safety Culture at PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II Hospital	Cross sectional quantitative approach with 66 nurses participating in this research	There is a positive and significant influence between the dimensions of transformational leadership and motivational factors on patient safety culture with a confidence level of 95%.
5.	Lappalainen <i>et al</i> [14]	The Relationship Between Nurse Manager's Transformational Leadership Style and Medication Safety	Descriptive analysis with 161 nurses participating in this research	There is a moderate but significant correlation between transformational leadership and medication safety as an effort to implement patient safety.

3.1. Implementation on Patient Safety Culture

Based on the results of the study, the transformational leadership style has a very strong relationship with the implementation of patient safety efforts in health service facilities, namely hospitals. Several public and private hospitals in Uzbekistan have implemented a transformational leadership style. The research results show that this leadership style can create better relationships with patients, thus supporting the implementation of patient safety. The results of research on three hospitals in Finland that implemented a transformational leadership style showed similar results. Transformational leadership increases the safety of treatment for patients. Treatment safety in medical procedures will support the implementation of patient safety in hospitals. Likewise, in Indonesia, the results of research conducted in several regions show the influence of transformational leadership style on the implementation of patient safety.

Transformational leadership is a leadership style with the characteristic that a leader can influence subordinates in a certain way so that they will feel appreciated [15]. Transformational leadership has undeniable reliability practically, especially theoretically [16]. Transformational leadership centres on a positive relationship with team innovation and the learning of individual members within a team [17]. This leadership is characterized by ideal influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual assessment [15]. In practice, this leadership style requires the involvement of the entire hospital.

Transformational leadership applied in hospitals is a very significant and positive strategy for implementing patient safety culture and perceptions of patient safety. By implementing transformational leadership, leaders can optimally facilitate a good work environment and provide a balance between job demands and the strength of job resources [18]. Transformational leadership is used as an important indicator that can help achieve health in the hospital industry in the aspects of quality of care, job satisfaction, and patient satisfaction. Good-quality care is one form of effort to implement patient safety. Good-quality care will reduce the risk of patient safety in hospitals. This risk reduction then has an impact on increasing job satisfaction for hospital staff as well as patient satisfaction.

3.2. Implementation on Hospital Risk Management

Transformational leadership also plays a significant role in improving working conditions and the atmosphere. Working conditions and atmosphere support officer motivation in carrying out their work. In hospitals, improving working

conditions and the atmosphere will enable staff to build relationships with patients through effective communication [19]. With positive relationships built by health and non-health workers in hospitals, efforts to improve service quality, reduce patient safety incidents, and achieve patient satisfaction will be carried out more easily and precisely.

Transformational leadership is considered capable of being applied by hospital leaders in carrying out clinical risk management, both in the process of providing safe services or care and in the process of improving the quality of care [20]. Clinical risk management is an effort to minimise or control losses resulting from clinical actions. The losses in question are related to patient safety. An increase in clinical risk will certainly endanger patient safety. Hospitals need to manage clinical risks comprehensively so as not to cause losses that result in reduced patient safety rates.

However, in implementing transformational leadership in hospitals, there are several things that a leader needs to pay attention to. First, hospital decision-makers might consider investing in the transformational leadership behaviours of their leaders by creating a combination of transformational leadership training and peer consultation. Training is carried out as an effort to increase the knowledge, abilities, and attitudes of officers in implementing patient safety. Consultation between colleagues is an effort carried out as a form of effective communication in seeking or determining alternative solutions to problems related to patient safety implementation actions. Second, hospital decision-makers must consider increasing hospital social capital which will influence quality and safety performance. The social capital in question is everything that influences relationships between individuals in an organization, such as norms, participative attitudes, trust, and so on. Effective communication is one of the basics for increasing social capital between colleagues in the hospital. Social capital needs to be built to equalize the perceptions of health and non-health workers in efforts to implement patient safety. This improvement can be done through the involvement of all hospital parties, both internal and external.

Before implementing a transformational leadership style, leaders must first gain knowledge about the characteristics of this style and apply it as a strategy in efforts to improve overall quality and patient safety. Knowledge related to transformational leadership can be obtained from various sources, such as research studies or field observations. Through the research conducted, leaders can better understand this leadership style and adapt it to the needs of the organization. This helps leaders' readiness to implement a transformational leadership style in hospitals. The focus on improving quality and patient safety begins with the leader's commitment to creating safety and quality of service for patients. The commitment built by hospital leaders will have an impact on the consistency of patient safety implementation efforts. In this case, it is necessary to determine strategic priorities and lay a strong foundation by taking several concrete steps to implement and develop patient safety efforts [21]. Developing patient safety efforts can, of course, be carried out by leaders taking steps to create and maintain a healthy patient safety culture and developing a patient safety program. Leaders need to plan and evaluate patient safety programs that have not yet been implemented or have been implemented in the hospital.

As a complex health service facility, hospitals aim to achieve patient satisfaction by providing optimal service and care. An important indicator of achieving this goal is striving for patient safety. With various characteristics, hospital leaders play a proactive role in carrying out management functions that can be adjusted to the needs of the organization. Leaders with a transformational leadership style will focus on effective integration processes so they can provide high-quality patient care [22]. Developing effective teamwork in the work environment is very necessary in this regard. Teamwork between healthcare members will overcome problems related to patient safety. Effective team performance can reduce medical errors and help hospitals operate more optimally at lower costs and with the highest levels of quality and efficiency.

4. Conclusion

The transformational leadership style has a very strong relationship with the implementation of patient safety efforts in healthcare facilities, namely hospitals. Transformational leadership is a leadership style with the characteristic that a leader can influence subordinates in a certain way so that they will feel appreciated. Transformational leadership applied in hospitals is a very significant and positive strategy for implementing patient safety culture and perceptions of patient safety. Transformational leadership also plays a significant role in improving working conditions and the atmosphere. With positive relationships built by health and non-health workers in hospitals, efforts to improve service quality, reduce patient safety incidents, and achieve patient satisfaction will be carried out more easily and precisely. Transformational leadership is considered capable of being applied by hospital leaders in carrying out clinical risk management, both in the process of providing safe services or care and in the process of improving the quality of care.

However, in implementing transformational leadership in hospitals, there are several things that a leader needs to pay attention to. Leaders might consider investing in the transformational leadership behaviours of their leaders by creating a combination of transformational leadership training and peer-to-peer consultation. Additionally, leaders should consider increasing hospital social capital, which will influence quality and safety performance. Social capital needs to be built to equalize the perceptions of health and non-health workers in efforts to implement patient safety. This improvement can be done through the involvement of all hospital parties, both internal and external. Before implementing a transformational leadership style, leaders must gain knowledge about the characteristics of this style and apply it as a strategy in efforts to improve overall quality and patient safety. The focus on improving quality and patient safety begins with the leader's commitment to creating safety and quality of service for patients. Leaders need to plan and evaluate patient safety programs that have not yet been implemented or have been implemented in the hospital. All these efforts are carried out to achieve the hospital's goal as a complex health service facility, namely to achieve patient satisfaction by providing optimal service and care. In this case, leaders play an important role in seeking interventions to implement patient safety in hospitals. With various characteristics, leaders with a transformational leadership style will focus on effective integration processes so that they can provide high-quality patient care to prevent patient safety incidents.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

Author acknowledges the reviewer's positive suggestions on this paper.

References

- [1] Oktaviani MH, Rofli M. An Overview of The Implementation of The Head of The Room's Supervision of Implementing Nurses In Patient Safety. *Journal of Nursing Leadership and Management*. 2019; 2(1): 23-27.
- [2] Rahmah NM, Sarwati P. Determinants of Management and Leadership Functions of Room Heads with Patient Safety Culture by Executive Nurses at Rs. Dr. Chasbullah Abdul Madjid. *Journal of Social and Human Incentives*. 2019; 2(2): 182-194.
- [3] Mulyatiningsih S, Sasyari U. Effective Leadership Styles in Improving Patient Safety. *Scientific Journal of Altruistic Nursing*. 2021; 4(1): 27-35.
- [4] Huriati H, Shalahuddin S, Hidayah N, Suaib S, Arfah A. Literature Review: Quality of Patient Safety Services In Hospitals. *In Economic Forum*. 2022; 24(1): 186-194.
- [5] Maharani, DW. The Influence of Leadership Style, Teamwork, Patient Safety Culture on Patient Safety Performance (Study of Employees at Ulin Hospital, Banjarmasin). Doctoral dissertation, Brawijaya University. 2019.
- [6] Salsabila AN, Dhamanti, I. Factors that Influence Nurses in Implementing Patient Safety in Hospitals: Literature Review. *Nursing Journal*. 2023; 7(1): 524-530.
- [7] Novianto AK, Sunariani NN. The Role of Leadership in Patient Safety Climate Through Teamwork and Management Performance. *Bali Health Journal*. 2021; 5(2): 79-92.
- [8] Cope V, Murray M. Leadership: Patient Safety Depends on It. *Collegian*. 2021; 28(6): 604-609.
- [9] Mistry MV, Seeta Devi A, Suji M, Yadav, P. Impact of Transformational Leadership on Patient Safety & Outcome—A Systematic Review. *Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology*. 2020; 14(4): 3797-3800.
- [10] Syabanasyah I, Rachmawati E, Hartono B. The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Patient Safety Efforts. *Journal of Health Science and Technology*. 2023; 10(2): 150-161.
- [11] Rizkia DG, Girsang AJ, Kusumapradja R, Hilmy MR, Pamungkas RA, Dewi S. The Effect of Interprofessional Collaboration and Transformational Leadership on Patient Safety with Work Motivation as Intervening Variables. *Journal of Economic Applications of Accounting and Business*. 2022; 4(2): 039-053.
- [12] Gao Y, Tangatarova S. Transformational Leadership and Patient Safety In Hospitals: The Roles of Safety Culture, Decision-Making Capacity, and Locus of Control. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*. 2021; 10(2): 106-122.

- [13] Azuma AP, Wahyuningsih RSH, Alviana F. The Influence of Transformational Leadership and Motivation on the Implementation of Patient Safety Culture at PKU Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta Unit II Hospital. *Health Scientific Journal*. 2020; 10(1): 62-69.
- [14] Lappalainen M, Härkänen M, Kvist T. The Relationship Between Nurse Manager's Transformational Leadership Style and Medication Safety. *Scandinavian Journal of Caring Sciences*. 2019; 34(2): 357-369.
- [15] Sinaga N, Aprilinda D, Budiman PA. Transformational Leadership Concept. *Indonesian Scientific Journal*. 2021; 1(7): 840–846.
- [16] Asbari M. Is Transformational Leadership Suitable for Future Organizational Needs?. *International Journal of Social, Policy, and Law*. 2020; 1(1): 51-55.
- [17] Klaic A, Burtscher MJ, Jonas K. Fostering Team Innovation and Learning Using Team-Centric Transformational Leadership: The Role of Teamwork Quality. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*. 2020; 93(4): 942-966.
- [18] Seljemo C, Viksveen P, Ree E. The Role of Transformational Leadership, Job Demands and Job Resources for Patient Safety Culture In Norwegian Nursing Homes: A Cross-Sectional Study. *BMC Health Services Research*. 2020; 20(799): 1-8.
- [19] Asif M, Jameel A, Hussain A, Hwang J, Sahito N. Linking Transformational Leadership with Nurse-Assessed Adverse Patient Outcomes and The Quality of Care: Assessing The Role of Job Satisfaction and Structural Empowerment. *International journal of environmental research and public health*. 2019; 16(13): 2381-2395.
- [20] Braithwaite J, Pfaff H. A Parsonian Approach to Patient Safety: Transformational Leadership and Social Capital as Preconditions for Clinical Risk Management—The GI Factor. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2020; 17(11): 3989-4001.
- [21] Engineer CY, Dhamanti I. From Hospital Readiness to Patient Safety: Building Leadership Capacity for Patient Safety in Indonesia. *Journal of Health Administration*. 2022; 10(2): 280–285.
- [22] Chakraborty S, Kaynak H, Pagán JA. Bridging Hospital Quality Leadership to Patient Care Quality. *International Journal of Production Economics*. 2021; 233: 108010.